

1 **Immunoglobulin-based therapeutic targeting for treatment of metastasis to the skeletal system:**
2 **FGF18.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We study breast cancer in humans as a model for understanding cancer as a system in its entirety and as
8 a life cycle, including cell of origin, transformation, subtype selection, biology and ecology of the primary
9 tumor, the tumor microenvironment, tumor immunology and surveillance, dissemination via the circulating
10 tumor cell, metastasis to the lymph nodes, and metastasis to distant sites. Metastasis is the major cause
11 of death from cancer and patients with breast cancer are at risk of developing one of four major
12 metastases to a distant site, and we have presented substantial evidence indicating that lymph node
13 metastasis is a precursor to (rather than simply a reflection of) metastasis to distant organ sites including
14 the CNS (1-5). We recently utilized whole transcriptome technologies to define the full complement of
15 differentially expressed kinases and phosphatases in HER2+ breast cancer: in the primary tumor, and in
16 metastasis to the CNS (6-8). Here we present information on a therapeutic target identified using whole
17 transcriptome technologies (9, 10) measuring total transcription in the bone metastases of humans with
18 breast cancer, comparing the bone metastatic transcriptome to the primary tumor transcriptome and to
19 normal cells from the breast. We identify a therapeutic target based on its optimized therapeutic index:
20 differential expression and up-regulation upon metastasis to the bone, FGF18, as a candidate therapeutic
21 target for the medical management of bone metastasis.
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the skeletal system to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the bone metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer: a therapeutic target for immunoglobulin-based targeting that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: FGF18.

Results

Figure 1: FGF18 is differentially expressed in bone metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

I. Bone metastases and normal mammary epithelial cells; human breast cancer.

n=3 normal mammary epithelial cells

n=3 bone metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1693483	3.89E-05	7.885045	1.740216	0.6904861	FGF18	5971/40614	85.3

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal cells of the breast and in bone metastases of humans with breast cancer (9), we discovered differential expression of fibroblast growth factor 18, encoded by *FGF18* in metastasis to the skeletal system in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of FGF18 changed more than 85% of the human bone metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 40,614 transcripts ("Rank"). Note that in this case however the positive fold-change indicated decreased quantity of FGF18 messenger RNA in bone metastases, demonstrating down-regulation of FGF18 during disease progression and dissemination in this setting or cohort.

II. Bone metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

n=3 cultured breast cancer cells, human (MCF7)

n=3 bone metastatic variant; cultured breast cancer cells, human (MCF7b)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
8817	6.81E-09	0.2932	-5.795435	-1.699103	42.68	FGF18	3781/20047	81.1

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in human breast cancer cells and in a bone metastatic variant of the same cell line (10), we validated differential expression of *FGF18* in metastasis to the skeletal system in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 2**). The expression of FGF18 changed more than 80% of the human bone metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 20,047 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of FGF18 messenger RNA in cells with propensity to metastasize to the skeletal system, demonstrating up-regulation of FGF18 during disease progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

1 Thus, differential and increased expression of FGF18 defines the bone metastatic transcriptome in
2 human breast cancer.

3 **Discussion**

4 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
5 treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
6 trastuzumab). Immunoglobulin-based inhibitors of FGF18 can immediately be tested for safety and
7 efficacy in experimental models of bone metastasis in patients with bone metastasis who have failed
8 previous treatment, with the ultimate goal of identifying the most effective inhibitors of bone metastasis in
9 humans with breast cancer who have not yet progressed but are at predicted high risk, or those whose
10 metastasis has not yet become unmanageable due to metastasis size, number or location. A multi-kinase
11 approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the
12 daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, targeting *CDKN* inactivation and ATP-binding
13 cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone
14 resistance (11).
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

References

1. Nolan E, Kang Y, Malanchi I. Mechanisms of Organ-Specific Metastasis of Breast Cancer. *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Med.* 2023 Nov 1;13(11):a041326. doi: 10.1101/cshperspect.a041326. PMID: 36987584; PMCID: PMC10626265.
2. Yip RKH, Rimes JS, Capaldo BD, et al. Mammary tumour cells remodel the bone marrow vascular microenvironment to support metastasis. *Nat Commun.* 2021;12(1):6920. Published 2021 Nov 26. doi:10.1038/s41467-021-26556-6.
3. Jackett KN, Browne AT, Aber ER, Clements M, Kaplan RN. How the bone microenvironment shapes the pre-metastatic niche and metastasis. *Nat Cancer.* 2024 Dec;5(12):1800-1814. doi: 10.1038/s43018-024-00854-6. Epub 2024 Dec 13. PMID: 39672975.
4. Yin JJ, Pollock CB, Kelly K. Mechanisms of cancer metastasis to the bone. *Cell Res.* 2005 Jan;15(1):57-62. doi: 10.1038/sj.cr.7290266. PMID: 15686629.
5. Liu, Y. and Cao, X., 2016. Characteristics and significance of the pre-metastatic niche. *Cancer cell*, 30(5), pp.668-681.
6. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Increased rate of CNS metastasis in patients with HER2+ breast cancer is a result of the intrinsic gene expression program of HER2+ subtype breast cancers, not a consequence of use of the HER2+-targeted drug trastuzumab.
7. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Kinase targeting in HER2+ breast cancer to prevent and treat CNS disease: CDK8.
8. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Catalytic site targeting in HER2+ breast cancer for the treatment of CNS metastasis: PPP1R3D.
9. Dataset 1: GSE55715. Johnson J, Bessette DC, Saunus JM, et al. Characterization of a novel breast cancer cell line derived from a metastatic bone lesion of a breast cancer patient. *Breast Cancer Res Treat.* 2018;170(1):179-188. doi:10.1007/s10549-018-4719-9.
10. Dataset 2: GSE121677. Clements ME, Johnson RW. PREX1 drives spontaneous bone dissemination of ER+ breast cancer cells. *Oncogene.* 2020;39(6):1318-1334. doi:10.1038/s41388-019-1064-3.
11. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Therapeutic targeting of catalytically available solid tumor vulnerabilities in human cancer.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Methods

We utilized GSE55715 (Dataset 1) for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the skeletal system (bones) and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE121677 [Dataset 2] for target validation) using microarray and RNA-sequencing data (published) and R-based computational methods for identification of therapeutic targets for immunoglobulin-based inhibition and clinical intervention.